

Chemical equilibrium studies on some bivalent transition metal chelates of biologically active molecules (drugs)

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Abstract : Stability constants of metal chelates of dicyclomine hydrochloride (dcm), metformin hydrochloride (mfm) drugs with the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} transition metal ions have been evaluated pH metrically in aqueous solution at 25 °C and 0.1 M (NaClO₄) fixed ionic strength. Proton ligand stability constant and metal ligand stability constant were determined by Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration techniques as modified by Irving and Rossotti.

Keywords : Transition metal complex, stability constant, ligand.

Introduction

The coordination chemistry of metal ion in aqueous solution is the vast field of investigation¹. It has been found that number of drugs are known to inhibit protein synthesis in bacteria by causing misreading of the genetic code². Metal complexes with sulpha drugs played a vital role in metabolic activity and toxicological function in biological systems³. The dcm-HCl is a muscle relaxant drug. It depresses all synapses on molar paths in the spinal cord. It has smooth muscle relaxant action in addition to weak anticholinergic effect, thereby being used as an antispasmodic agent⁴. The mfm-HCl suppress hepatic glucon eogenesis and inhibit intestinal absorption of glucose. It interferes with mitochondrial respiratory chains from peripheral glucose utilization by enhancing anaerobic glycolysis.

The present communication deals with the study of pH-potentiometric determination of formation constants of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} transition metal complexes with dcm-HCl and mfm-HCl using Irving-Rossotti technique⁵.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of high grade of purity. Pure drugs were obtained as a gift sample from a reputed

pharmaceutical industry (Sun Pharma, Baroda). All these solutions were prepared in double distilled CO₂ free water. All these solutions were standardized before use by known methods⁶.

pH measurement were made with Elico digital pH meter (Model LI-120, Elico Pvt. Ltd., Hyderabad accuracy ± 0.01) with combined glass electrode. All the solutions were allowed to attain equilibrium at 25 °C and titrated with standard carbonate free NaOH solution (0.2 M) at fixed ionic strength (0.1 M, NaClO₄).

The results obtained for each titration is plotted as a volume of NaOH added vs pH and corresponding volume at successive pH for each set is determined and calculated.

Results and discussion

Proton ligand stability constant (log K_{HL}^H) :

Proton ligand stability constant of these two ligands were determined by pointwise calculation as well as half integral method. The average number of proton associated with ligand (n_A) were calculated from acid and ligand titration curves and used to obtain pK_a values. The pK_a values were also checked using linear plot method (plot – log $n_A / 1 - n_A$ vs pH) and was found in good agreement. All the pK_a values of ligand are shown in Table 1.

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Table 1. Proton ligand stability constant and metal ligand stability constant

Sr. no.	Ligand	$\log K_{HL}^H$	$\log K_{ML}^M$		
			Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}
1.	(dcm-HCl)	$a = 1.87$	$a = 3.07$	$a = 3.09$	$a = 3.81$
		$b = 1.90$	$b = 3.06$	$b = 3.07$	$b = 3.10$
		$c = 1.88$	$c = 3.07$	$c = 3.09$	$c = 3.45$
2.	(mfm-HCl)	$a = 6.64$	$a = 6.36$	$a = 6.35$	$a = 5.85$
		$b = 6.60$	$b = 6.34$	$b = 6.34$	$b = 5.61$
		$c = 6.62$	$c = 6.35$	$c = 6.35$	$c = 5.73$

a = Pointwise, b = half neutralization, c = mean.

From Table 1 it is clearly understood that mfm-HCl have the highest pK_a value due to primary amino group (-NH₂) whereas dcm-HCl has lower value due to tertiary ($\geq N$) amino group and electron donating effects of two ethyl group attached to nitrogen donor atom as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1

Metal ligand stability constant ($\log K_{ML}^M$):

$\log K_{ML}^M$ of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} transition metal complexes with these drugs were calculated by pointwise calculation method and as well as half integral method (n^- vs pL). The values of n^- (metal ligand formation number) and pL (free ligand concentration) were used to calculate the $\log K$ values of the transition metal ions with all ligands.

The pH of hydrolysis was determined for each metal ion to know complex formation before hydrolysis of metal ions.

Considerable separation of metal complex curve from reagent curve along volume axis is an evidence for complex formation. The highest values of n was around one, indicating the formation of 1 : 1 complex for all metal ions with both drugs. Further the use of very dilute solution of metal ions, ruled out the formation of polynuclear complexes.

It is found that stability constant increases with increase in atomic number of metal and follows the order of Irving and Williams series. This order is particularly valid for most O-N donor ligands⁷: Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II}.

Low values of pK_a indicate that both drugs are quite suitable for complexation at optimum physiological condition. This may favour the binding of drugs with nucleic acid of cell via transition metal and helps in transportation of drugs to the site of its physiological action.

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